

Title: Periglacial puzzles: Unravelling environmental controls on alpine solifluction lobe dimensions and shape

Short Running title: Controls on alpine solifluction lobes

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Abstract

Freeze-thaw processes cause periglacial creep (solifluction) which forms solifluction lobes: lobate features characterized by a steep riser (front) and a smooth tread (body). Despite the widespread occurrence of these lobes, the controls on their morphometry remain poorly understood. Research into solifluction lobe morphometry is crucial for understanding their role in landscape evolution, hydrology, sediment budgets, and providing microhabitats in a warming climate.

We mapped geomorphic and vegetation properties of 40 solifluction lobes in the Turtmann Valley, Swiss Alps, and recorded soil moisture and temperature with a TOMST TMS4 logger at a 10-minute interval for nearly two years. We combined these data with derivatives of a high-resolution digital elevation model and conducted a Spearman ranked correlation test. Our results revealed that: (i) The largest lobes, with the highest risers occur in areas with high flow accumulation ($\rho = 0.40-0.75$). (ii) Wider, lobate lobes dominate at higher elevations ($\rho = 0.49$) on north-exposed slopes ($\rho = 0.53$) with long snow ($\rho = 0.47-0.58$) and sparse vegetation cover, while narrow, tongue-shaped lobes occur at lower elevations with high vegetation cover ($\rho = 0.38-0.55$), suggesting a strong topoclimatic control. (iii) Lobes in the Turtmann Valley are longer and more tongue-shaped, with higher risers and on steeper slopes, than many lobes previously studied. Overall, our results suggest that alpine solifluction lobe dimensions and shape are controlled by different set of environmental factors than arctic lobes, possibly due to effects of stronger topoclimatic gradients, steeper slopes and higher flow accumulation on mountain slopes.

1. Introduction

Solifluction is the process of slow downslope movement of soil associated with freeze-thaw action, common in periglacial environments (e.g., Benedict, 1970; Matsuoka, 2001). Solifluction comprises four processes: needle-ice creep, frost creep, gelifluction and plug-like flow (Matsuoka, 2001). These

solifluction processes create landforms as solifluction lobes, which are key components of periglacial landscapes (Glade et al., 2021; Ridefelt and Boelhouwers, 2006). Solifluction lobes consist of a steep riser and a relatively smooth tread (Fig. 1d; Matsuoka et al., 2005) and are differentiated into turf-banked (TBL) and stone-banked lobes (SBL). TBLs consist of non-sorted materials where at least the riser is covered by vegetation, while SBLs are sorted lobes that are not vegetated (Benedict, 1970; Matsuoka, 2001). For TBLs to develop, the sediment flow should be channelized, soil movement should decrease downslope and strong vertical frost sorting should be absent (Benedict, 1970; Benedict, 1976). Glade et al. (2021) compared the formation of solifluction lobes to fluid fingering, suggesting that they form due to the competition between gravity and soil cohesion. Eichel et al. (2017) suggest that root cohesion provided by vegetation may supply the cohesion needed at the lobe front.

Solifluction lobes occur in all periglacial environments but their size (length, width, riser height) and shape (length-width ratio) varies greatly between and within different regions. Matsuoka (2001) analysed data from 46 sites all over the world and found riser heights typically ranged between 0.2-2 m, while tread width and length ranged between 2-50 m. To explain the variation of lobe size and shape, previous studies investigated environmental factors such as elevation and soil moisture. For solifluction lobes in the Arctic Abisko region, Ridefelt and Boelhouwers (2006) found that riser height, tread length and width decrease with increasing elevation and decreasing soil moisture content. In the Arctic Kluane Range, Hugenholtz and Lewkowicz (2002) revealed that tread length and width increase with increasing organic mat content, higher soil fines content and reduced active-layer thaw depth, resulting in larger lobe dimensions downslope. In contrast, high risers were related to thin organic mats, thick active-layers and high coarse particle content (Hugenholtz and Lewkowicz, 2002). Lobe shape can be expressed as lobe-width-ratio and differentiated into tongue-shaped ($L/W \geq 1$) and lobate ($L/W < 1$) forms (Matsuoka et al., 2005). As lobate TBLs were found in several mountain regions, at Outpost Mountains (Hugenholtz and Lewkowicz, 2002), Canadian Rockies (Smith, 1987a), Tien Shan (Gengnian et al., 1995) and Mt Kosciusko (Costin et al., 1967), Hugenholtz and Lewkowicz (2002)

suggested that turf-banked solifluction lobes develop a characteristic lobate shape independent of the regional environment and of site-specific influences. However, assessment of environmental controls based on two Arctic studies (Hugenholtz and Lewkowicz, 2002; Ridefelt and Boelhouwers, 2006) found partially contrasting results, limiting generalizations. In addition, Alpine environments are characterized by a topography with steeper slopes and higher elevations and therefore, it remains questionable if findings from the Arctic can be transferred to mountain regions and if environmental controls play the same important role as in the Arctic. Especially since topographic heterogeneity might be a key factor controlling lobe width (Matsuoka et al., 2005).

Alpine and Arctic environments experience extraordinarily strong warming (Biskaborn et al., 2019; Hock et al., 2019), altering periglacial process frequency, magnitude and distribution (Aalto et al., 2017; Biskaborn et al., 2019) and environmental controls (Choler et al., 2024; Pepin et al., 2022), which, in turn, influence vegetation change (Heijmans et al., 2022) or increase geomorphic hazards and risk in the Arctic (Hjort et al., 2022). Therefore, an understanding of environmental controls on periglacial processes such as solifluction is needed to predict landscape evolution and assess ecosystem resilience. Rising temperatures and changing snowfall regimes will affect solifluction movement rates (Aalto et al., 2017; Ridefelt et al., 2010), which in turn can affect sediment erosion, storage and deposition and catchment sediment budgets. Furthermore, widespread solifluction lobes can, depending on their size (Eichel et al., 2017), provide important carbon and water storage (e.g. Fröjd et al., 2024; Reato et al., 2021), as well as microrefugia for alpine species threatened by climate (Gentili et al., 2015), increasing alpine landscape and ecosystem resilience. In order to predict how solifluction lobes and their functions may be affected by climate change, we must first understand by which climatic or environmental factors they are most affected.

To unravel key controls on solifluction lobe size and shape, we (1) mapped solifluction lobes in the Turtmann Valley, Swiss Alps and quantified their dimensions and (2) quantified environmental factors, including slope gradient, soil temperature, soil moisture content, snow duration, vegetation and

material properties. Furthermore, we compared our findings to collected lobe dimensions from Arctic and Alpine environments.

2. Study area

We investigated 40 solifluction lobes in the Turtmann Valley and its hanging valleys in the Swiss Alps (Fig. 1ab). The Turtmann Valley is a South-North oriented tributary to the 110 km² large Rhône Valley, characterized by a Pleistocene glacial trough and 15 hanging valleys. The hanging valleys (or *tälli/telli*) contain periglacial creep landforms such as rock glaciers (Nyenhuis et al., 2005), as well as widespread solifluction lobes (Otto and Dikau, 2004). The investigated solifluction lobes are located at elevations between 2187 and 2683 m and were formed on lateral moraine slopes, talus slopes, hillslopes and a rock glacier front. Mean annual air temperature (MAAT) for the years 2000 to 2023, measured at nearby meteorological station Oberer Stelligletscher located at 2914 m and adjusted to lobe elevations by applying a temperature lapse rate of 6 °C/km, revealed MAATs between 0.18 °C (highest lobes) and 3.00 °C (lowest lobes) (MeteoSwiss, 2024). According to the permafrost distribution model by Kenner et al. (2019), 1/3 of the solifluction lobes are potentially underlain by permafrost which could affect their size (Fig. S1). Precipitation measured at 2180 m ranged between 648 and 931 mm/year in the years 2013 to 2022, with an average of 784 mm/year (MeteoSwiss, 2022).

Figure 1. a) Location of the Turtmann Valley within Switzerland and **b)** location of the solifluction lobes within the study area in seven different hanging valleys (Orthophoto by SwissTopo). **c, d, e)** Examples of solifluction lobes in the study area, with a schematic sketch of a lobe and different lobe elements in **(d)**.

The “moraine” solifluction lobes (Fig. 1) occurred on lateral moraine slopes formed by the Little Ice Age and 1920 glacier advance of the Turtmann Glacier (Eichel et al., 2020; Eichel et al., 2018). The lobes in Brändjitellet, Blüomatttälli and Grüobtälli were formed on talus slopes while lobes at Giigigrat and most of the lobes in Piipjitellet were formed on valley slopes consisting of moraine material from the Last Glacial Maximum. The highest elevated lobes in Piipjitellet were formed on an inactive rock glacier front (Nyenhuis et al., 2005).

3. Methods

3.1. Lobe size and shape

We mapped 40 solifluction lobes based on 0.1 m resolution orthophotos (swissImage10) and 0.5 m resolution DEMs (swissAlti3D) in ArcGIS Pro 3.3.0 and derived maximum lobe width and length (Fig. 1d). Lobe size was validated in the field, and riser height was quantified as an additional size-indicative variable. Lobe shape can be differentiated by the length-width-ratio (L/W), with $L/W > 1$ indicating tongue-shaped forms and $L/W < 1$ indicating lobate-shaped forms (Matsuoka et al., 2005; Wahrhaftig and Cox, 1959).

3.2. Environmental controlling factors

3.2.1. Topographic controlling factors

For each lobe the mean elevation, the dominant aspect, maximum flow accumulation and mean tread slope angle, usually a few degrees smaller than parent slope angle (Hugenholtz and Lewkowicz, 2002), were derived from DEMs using ArcGIS Pro. For further statistical analysis, the lobe aspect was transformed into northing and easting using the cosine and sine of the measured aspect (Leyer and Wesche, 2007). The maximum flow accumulation factor is a simple indicator for the potential water and sediment input. We collected a surface soil sample in the centre of the widest part of the lobe, usually located at the frontal part of the lobe tread. Soil material were processed in the laboratory with wet sieving and gravitational sedimentation analysis (DIN 18123, 2011) to determine fine material content (silt and clay <0.063 mm).

3.2.2. Topoclimatic controlling factors

To continuously measure soil temperature and moisture content in the solifluction lobes, a TOMST TMS4 logger was placed in the frontal part of each lobe tread in August 2022. TOMST loggers are equipped with three temperature sensors with an accuracy of ± 0.5 °C and one soil moisture sensor with unknown accuracy (Wild et al., 2019). We monitored soil temperature with an interval of 10 minutes between September 1st, 2022 and June 30th, 2024, at 0.22 m and 0.05 m depth and 0.1 m

above the ground. Soil moisture was measured at 0.13 m depth. For statistical analysis, we only used soil temperature at 0.05 m depth and soil moisture. Logger data was analysed using the MyClim R package (R v2024.04.2+764) specifically developed for these loggers (Man et al., 2023). To reduce noise, we aggregated the data into hourly intervals using the R packages dplyr (Wickham et al., 2023) and lubridate (Grolemund and Wickham, 2011).

Soil moisture was recorded as raw moisture signal pulses, which needed to be transformed into volumetric water content (VWC) (-) during pre-processing of the data (Man et al., 2023). We used the 'universal' soil type for logger calibration, as no differences between soil type specific calibration curves and the 'universal' calibration curve were observed by previous studies (Kemppinen et al., 2023; Kopecký et al., 2021). To compare temperature properties between investigated lobes, we calculated mean annual ground temperature (MAGT) using the periods September 1st, 2022 – August 31st, 2023, and July 1st, 2023 – June 30th, 2024, the mean summer ground temperature (MSGT) for the months June 2023 until August 2023 and the mean winter ground temperature (MWGT) for the months December until February (2022/2023, 2023/2024). Freezing degree days (FDD) were calculated as the sum of the negative temperatures for the period September 1st, 2022 – August 31st, 2023 and July 1st, 2023 – June 30th, 2024. Both periods were comparable as no freezing occurred during July and August 2023. To analyse soil moisture content, mean and cumulative soil moisture content were calculated for the entire almost two-year measurement period.

To assess the influence of snow cover on ground freezing, we calculated the snow cover duration using a method adapted from Schmid et al. (2012) . Snow cover is present when the standard deviation of daily ground temperature is below 0.3 °C for negative ground temperatures or below 0.1 °C for positive temperatures below 3 °C. The script determines the number of snow cover days by checking each day whether it meets the criteria and sums these days up. To assess timing of snow melt, we derived the snow ripening date (RD) and melt-out date (MD) from the temperature and soil moisture data (Fig. S2). The RD indicates the start of the zero curtain when liquid water from surface snow

melting infiltrates and warms the ground at logger level (0.05 m) through release of latent heat during freezing (Schmid et al., 2012). In our data, the RD was characterized by a sudden increase of 0.005 in the volumetric water content and a ground temperature of $0 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The MD indicates the end of the zero curtain effect, when the isolating effect of snow cover disappears (Schmid et al., 2012) and ground temperature rises above 0.5°C . The melt duration was calculated as the time between RD and MD. As a proxy for moisture input by snow melt, the cumulative soil moisture during melt was calculated as the sum of the positive soil moisture differences for each hour during the determined melt period. As snow cover, RD, MD, melt duration and FDD were absent during July and August, the applied time periods of September 2022 until August 2023 and July 2023 until June 2024 are not affecting our results. For the statistical analysis averaged values were used.

3.2.3. Vegetation controlling factors

Vegetation cover per lobe (%) was estimated from orthophotos. As an additional vegetation indicator, we calculated the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) from Sentinel 2 satellite imagery (Huang et al., 2021; Obuchowicz et al., 2024):

$$NDVI = \frac{(NIR - RED)}{(NIR + RED)} \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

Here, NIR is the near-infrared and RED is the red band of the satellite. NDVI values range between -1 and 1, with negative values representing water, values close to 0 representing land cover such as rocks, sand or concrete, low NDVI values representing sparse vegetation and high NDVI values representing healthy, dense vegetation (Huang et al., 2021). The calculations were performed using Google Earth Engine (Amiri and Pourghasemi, 2022; Velastegui-Montoya et al., 2023), where image composites for summer were selected based on Sentinel 2 images with less than 10% cloud cover. The NDVI was calculated for summers (June, July, August) 2023 and 2024, their summer means were taken as input for the statistical analyses.

3.3. Statistical analysis of controlling environmental factors

To determine which environmental factors, or combination of factors, control solifluction lobe dimension, we performed a Spearman ranked correlation test. In contrast to e.g., Pearson's correlation, this non-parametric test does not require a normal distribution of the data, making it suitable for our mostly non-normally distributed data (McCarroll, 2017). Using Spearman ranked correlation test, we tested the strength of relationships between the variables (ρ) and determined the significance (p-values). All p-values < 0.05 were considered significant.

4. Results

4.1. Lobe dimensions

Instrumented lobes were located at elevations between 2189 m and 2683 m with highest density between 2450 and 2500 m (Fig. 2). Our data revealed that the 40 measured lobes were between 3 and 97 m long, with an average of 28 m and the longest lobes occurring between 2350 and 2600 m elevation (Fig. 2a). Lobe width ranged from 4 to 59 m, 18 m on average, with an elevation pattern similar to lobe length (Fig. 2b). The average riser height was 1.8 m with a range between 0.4 and 7.5 m and largest risers occurring above 2350 m (Fig. 2c). The lobe area ranged between 17 and 3,351 m², with an average size of 575 m² (Fig. 2d). The L/W ratio was between 0.6 and 8.46 with an average of 1.5, showing no elevational trend (Fig. 2e). Lobe tread angle ranged from 14.3 to 37.5° with an average slope of 31°. Most lobes had tread angles steeper than 30°, especially lobes located above 2300 m (Fig. 2f).

Figure 2. Distribution of **a)** lobe width, **b)** length, **c)** riser height, **d)** area, **e)** length-width ratio, **f)** tread angle, **g)** aspect, **h)** flow accumulation and **i)** fine material content along elevation for the 40 studied lobes in the Turtmann Valley. Note that flow accumulation is on a logarithmic scale.

4.2. Observed environmental factors

The majority of the instrumented lobes are north facing (i.e., a northing close to 1.0) (Fig. 2g). The flow accumulation ranged from 10^3 to 10^6 cells showing a slight increasing trend with elevation (Fig. 2h). Most lobes revealed a soil fines content between 20 and 50 % with four lobes exceeding 70 % (Fig. 2i). The MAGT was between 0.71 and 5.15 °C revealing a decreasing trend with elevation (Fig. 3a). MSGT was between 6.9 and 13 °C and MWGT between -5.2 and 1°C with most lobes slightly below the freezing point. FDD ranged from -700 to 0°C Days (Fig. 3b). Mean volumetric water content (VWC, as an indicator for soil moisture) was 0.03 to 0.3 (Fig. 3c), cumulative moisture between 2725 and 30,8326 (Fig. 3d) and cumulative moisture during snow melt between 0.1 and 5.6 (Fig. 3e). The snow cover duration ranged from 125 to 229 days showing a slight increasing trend with elevation (Fig. 3f). The snow ripening date (RD) and melt-out date (MD) showed peaks in late April to early May for RD and late May to early June for MD (Fig. 3g). Melt duration revealed a slight increasing trend with elevation with values between 17 and 57 days (Fig. 3h). NDVI values were between 0 and 0.3 in

autumn and 0 and 0.4 in summer and revealed a decreasing trend with elevation (Fig. 3i). Vegetation cover was between 0 and 100 %, also showing a decreasing trend with elevation (Fig. 3j).

Figure 3. Distribution of soil temperature factors **a)** mean annual ground temperature (MAGT), mean summer ground temperature (MSGT) and mean winter ground temperature (MWGT) and **b)** freezing degree days (FDD); soil moisture factors **c)** mean soil moisture, **d)** cumulative soil moisture and **e)** cumulative soil moisture during snow melt; snow cover factors **f)** snow duration, **g)** snow ripening date (RD) and melt-out date (MD), **h)** melt duration; and vegetation factors **i)** NDVI and **j)** vegetation cover along elevation. Note that the FDD are positive here, so that a higher FDD means more freezing.

4.3. Environmental factors controlling lobe dimensions and shape

Lobe width and length were strongly correlated with each other ($\rho = 0.84$) and resulting lobe area ($\rho = 0.88-0.93$; Fig. 4). Furthermore, longer, wider and overall bigger lobes also have higher risers ($\rho = 0.44-0.47$). From the studied environmental factors, flow accumulation appeared to be the most important factor controlling lobe dimensions, with highest positive correlations to lobe width ($\rho = 0.75$), lobe length ($\rho = 0.69$), area ($\rho = 0.72$) and riser height ($\rho = 0.40$). Lobe width showed strong

positive correlations with elevation ($\rho = 0.49$), northern aspects ($\rho = 0.53$) and the snow-related variables snow cover duration ($\rho = 0.41$), RD ($\rho = 0.51$) and MD ($\rho = 0.38$). In contrast, lobe width was negatively related to MAGT ($\rho = -0.47$) and MSGT ($\rho = -0.58$), mean soil moisture ($\rho = -0.33$), cumulative soil moisture ($\rho = -0.33$), NDVI ($\rho = -0.55$) and total vegetation cover ($\rho = -0.38$). This pattern suggested that wider lobes dominate at higher elevations, on slopes with northern aspects and longer snow cover durations with late snow melt. Lobe length has similar, but weaker, correlations as lobe width (longer lobes on northern aspects ($\rho = 0.35$), with colder MGST ($\rho = -0.35$) and later RD ($\rho = 0.35$)). Additionally, lobe length is positively correlated with slope, indicating longer lobes on steeper slopes ($\rho = 0.32$).

Lobe area revealed positive correlations with elevation ($\rho = 0.36$), slope ($\rho = 0.34$), northern aspects ($\rho = 0.47$), snow cover duration ($\rho = 0.34$), RD ($\rho = 0.40$) and MD ($\rho = 0.37$) and negative correlations with MAGT ($\rho = -0.32$), MSGT ($\rho = -0.47$) and NDVI ($\rho = -0.42$). Besides flow accumulation, riser height correlated positively with MD ($\rho = 0.33$). Overall, these patterns suggest that the biggest lobes with highest risers occur on north-facing slopes with high flow accumulation, late snow melt, low annual and summer ground temperatures and sparse vegetation.

Positive correlations between lobe L/W ratios and MAGT ($\rho = 0.43$), MSGT ($\rho = 0.37$), MWGT ($\rho = 0.43$), freezing degree days ($\rho = 0.41$), NDVI ($\rho = 0.45$), and total vegetation cover ($\rho = 0.41$), combined with a negative correlation with elevation ($\rho = -0.46$) indicate that tongue-shaped lobes ($L/W > 1$) occur at lower elevations with year-round higher ground temperatures, low freezing intensities and dense vegetation, while lobate lobes favoured high elevations and northern aspects.

We found no significant correlations between lobe morphometry and easting, fine material content, cumulative moisture during melt or melt duration.

Figure 4. Heatmap of Spearman correlation coefficients between lobe dimensions on the x-axis and topographic, topoclimatic (temperature, soil moisture and snow) and vegetation factors on the y-axis. Bold values indicate statistical significance (p-value < 0.05).

5. Discussion

5.1. Flow accumulation controls solifluction lobe size

Our results showed that flow accumulation is a key factor for lobe size, with positive correlations between flow accumulation and lobe length, width, riser height and area (Fig. 4). Flow accumulation, in this study calculated from a digital elevation model, indicates how connected a lobe is to its upstream area, and how large this upstream area is. Thus, our results suggest that largest lobes develop where there is high potential for water and sediment input (Fig. 5a). This matches findings from laboratory tests and field measurements, which revealed that solifluction movement requires high soil moisture and that upslope material input contributes to lobe formation (Matthews et al., 1986). Research at a solifluction lobe in Jotunheimen (Norway) revealed that solifluction lobes form and grow by a mixture of solifluction movement and colluvial upslope input (Matthews et al., 1986). Solifluction movement results from high pore water pressures at the thaw-freeze interface of ice lenses during thaw consolidation (Fioleau et al., 2024; Harris et al., 2008a; Harris et al., 2008b). These high pore pressures arise from water released from thawing soil (Fioleau et al., 2024; Harris et al., 2008b; Kinnard and Lewkowicz, 2005) but also from additional water released by melting of snow patches (Jaesche et al., 2003; Price, 1971). When upslope water enters the solifluction lobe it gets channelized between its lateral risers, as demonstrated by ground water level measurements (Benedict, 1970; Harris, 1977; Harris, 1981) or geophysical measurements (Draebing and Eichel, 2017). Thus, hillslope water supply, as indicated by flow accumulation, can promote solifluction movement and thereby the formation of large lobes.

Flow accumulation also shows a significant negative correlation with NDVI, which in turn shows a significant negative correlation with lobe width and area (Fig. 4 and Fig. S3). This could indicate that areas with high flow accumulation, and thus high potential water and sediment input, are too active for an extensive vegetation cover to establish (Glade et al., 2021; Eichel et al., 2018; Eichel

et al., 2023b). The lack of vegetation cover in turn results in unstable slopes, facilitating the formation of large solifluction lobes (Hjort, 2014; Eichel et al., 2017; Oliva et al., 2009a) (Fig. 5a).

Figure 5. Schematic illustrations of **a)** flow accumulation and **b)** elevation control on size and shape of solifluction lobes in the Turtmann Valley.

Both studies by Ridefelt and Boelhouwers (2006) and Hugenholtz and Lewkowicz (2002) suggest that large lobes with high risers are related to higher fine material and moisture content, the latter increased by snow melt. Our data revealed no significant correlation of riser height to soil moisture, but significant relations between lobe dimensions and snow parameters such as snow cover duration, ripening and melt out date (Fig. 4). Missing correlations with soil moisture could result from logger locations close to the surface, not measuring soil moisture at the depths where movement occurs. In contrast to both studies from the Arctic, our results showed no significant correlations of fine material content with riser height or lobe size (Fig. 4). We suggest that other controls are stronger and overshadow any potential effects of fine material content in the Alpine Turtmann Valley. Riser height can further be amplified by higher soil cohesion (Glade et al., 2021), increased root cohesion (Eichel et al., 2017) or higher boulder content acting as obstacles (Draebing and Eichel, 2017; Matthews et al., 1986).

5.2 Topoclimatic gradients control alpine solifluction lobe shape

Our results suggest that alpine solifluction lobe shape (L/W ratio) depends on elevation and its interplay with soil temperatures, snow and vegetation along a topoclimatic gradient (Fig. 3,4 and 5b). We found wider, lobate lobes at high elevations with lowest temperatures, longer snow cover with later RDs and MDs, and lower vegetation cover and NDVI. At lower elevations with warmer conditions, shorter snow cover and more vegetation, with higher NDVI, narrower, tongue-shaped lobes dominate (Fig. 4 and 5b).

With increasing elevation, temperature decreases as shown by decreasing trends of MAGT, MSGT and MWGT (Fig. 3a and 4). Lower temperatures increase susceptibility to freezing indicated by more freezing degree days (Fig. 3b) and promote ice lens formation (Peppin and Style, 2013; Rempel, 2007). As snow cover is elevation-dependent (Grünewald and Lehning, 2011; Lehning et al., 2011; Theurillat et al., 2003), higher elevations are characterized by longer snow cover duration, and later ripening and melt out dates (Figs. 3 and 4). Snow insulates the ground and can decrease ground freezing (Luetschg and Haeberli, 2005), but also prolongs freezing conditions (Luetschg and Haeberli, 2005) enabling more ice lens formation and frost heave (Rempel, 2007), which increase thaw consolidation (Morgenstern and Nixon, 1971) and solifluction movement (Fiolleau et al., 2024). In addition, increased snow cover can result in more snowmelt supporting pore pressure increase while thawing and amplifying solifluction movement (Jaesche et al., 2003; Price, 1971). We further observed a decreasing trend of vegetation indicated by NDVI (Fig. 3i) and vegetation cover (Fig. 3j) with increasing elevation (Fig. 4). Vegetation increases root cohesion (Eichel et al., 2017) which fixes lobe sediments and decreases solifluction lobe movement (Glade et al., 2021). Together, all these elevation dependent factors suggest stronger movement at higher elevations, creating wide, lobate lobes. In contrast, tongue-shaped, possibly more slowly moving lobes dominate at lower elevations (Figs. 2,4 and 5b)

Overall, our elevation-related trend in solifluction lobe shape contradicts previous studies that found negative correlations between elevation and lobe dimensions (Hugenholtz and Lewkowicz, 2002; Oliva et al., 2009; Ridefelt and Boelhouwers, 2006). They explain the occurrence of larger, wider and longer lobes with higher risers at lower elevations by increased fine and organic matter contents, longer snow cover duration and increased vegetation (Hugenholtz and Lewkowicz, 2002; Ridefelt and Boelhouwers, 2006). Contrasting results could be explained by differences in snow and fine material distribution between arctic and alpine slopes. While Ridefelt and Boelhouwers (2006) observed the longest snow cover duration in the shielded, lower lying valleys, we found longest snow cover duration at highest elevations in Turtmann Valley (Fig. 3f). In addition, in our study site fine material content did not significantly increase downslope and seems unrelated to elevation and we found that long, but narrow lobes dominated under highest vegetation cover (Figs. 2i and 4). This suggests that alpine lobe dimensions and shape are controlled by different environmental factors than Arctic lobe properties, possibly due to effects of stronger topoclimatic gradients. This is reflected in the mean tread slope found in previous studies (10 to 20°) compared to our mean slope of 31° (Matsuoka et al., 2005; Smith, 1987; Matthews et al., 1986; Costin et al., 1967; Gengnian et al., 1995; Oliva et al., 2008; Oliva et al., 2009; Ridefelt and Boelhouwers, 2006; Hugenholtz and Lewkowics, 2002; Douglas and Harrison, 1996, Table S1).

5.3 Size and shape comparison with previously studied solifluction lobes

Several studies made solifluction lobe inventories in the past (Matsuoka et al., 2005; Smith, 1987b; Matthews et al., 1986; Costin et al., 1967; Gengnian et al., 1995; Oliva et al., 2008, 2009; Ridefelt and Boelhouwers, 2006; Hugenholtz and Lewkowics, 2002; Douglas and Harrison, 1996), providing information on mean lengths, widths, L/W ratios, riser heights and tread slopes of solifluction lobes in their study areas (Table S1). A comparison of these studies with our data reveals that the lobes in the Turtmann Valley are considerably longer than in the other study areas, with a mean length of 28.3 m compared to mean lengths between 2.6 and 15.4 m for the other sites (Fig. 6). With a mean width of

18.2 m, the lobes in the Turtmann Valley are also wider than the lobes in all study areas but Outpost Mountain (1.6 to 16.5 m, 20.9 m at Outpost Mountain (Hugenholtz and Lewkowicz, 2002)), indicating that the lobes in the Turtmann Valley are overall larger. Matsuoka et al. (2005) suggested that lobe length grows until changes in climate, slope or sediment availability occur. Maximum tread length depends on climatic and dynamic conditions and time (Matsuoka et al., 2005). A few of the studies provide lobe ages from ^{14}C dating which suggest that lobes are 1550 to 4500 years old. The ages range from 1560 ± 160 years at Outpost Mountains (Kinnard and Lewkowicz, 2006), 1610 – 3909 years at Southern Canadian Rockies (Smith, 1987c; Smith, 1993), 2910 ± 130 years at Mt Kosciuszko (Costin et al., 1967), 3309 ± 92 years at Sierra Nevada (Oliva et al., 2009) to 4470 ± 120 ^{14}C at Jotunheimen (Matthews et al., 1986). Lobes in the Turtmann Valley occur partially on lateral moraines formed during the LIA, on postglacial landforms such as the apex of talus slopes or on fronts of inactive rock glaciers, and they have characteristic longitudinal form indicating a mature stage and younger age (Curry, 2025). Therefore, increased time for lobe evolution can be excluded as the main driver for larger lobe length in Turtmann Valley. We suggest that observed lobe length is a result of better sediment availability and connectivity as suggested by high flow accumulation (Fig. 4) in combination with high slope angles indicated by tread angles, which are significantly correlated to lobe length and area (Fig. 3f, and 4). Our lobes revealed mean tread angles of $31 \pm 5^\circ$ which exceed tread angles of all other sites (on average 6 - 18.8°) (Table S1). Tread angles are usually $1\text{-}5^\circ$ lower than slope angles (Hugenholtz and Lewkowicz, 2002; Ridefelt and Boelhouwers, 2006) and latter control solifluction movement (Matsuoka, 2001). Therefore, we conclude that the greater slope angle, possibly in combination with flow accumulation, is responsible for the large lobe lengths and sizes observed in Turtmann Valley. The lobe lengths in the Turtmann Valley greatly exceed lobe widths, resulting in tongue-shaped solifluction lobes with L/W ratio > 1 . Only solifluction lobes at Sierra Nevada (Oliva et al., 2009) and Skaftafell (Douglas and Harrison, 1996) revealed a tongue-shaped form, while lobes at all other sites show a lobate shape with widths exceeding lengths (Fig. 6c).

The lobes in the Turtmann Valley have the highest mean risers (1.8 m) compared to other studies (0.4 - 1.0 m; Fig. 6a-b), with the exception of the lobes in the Tianshan Mountains (mean 1.8 m; Gengnian et al., 1995). The depth of movement, which characterizes the riser height, is controlled by the freezing depth (Matsuoka et al., 2005). The global analysis by Matsuoka (2001) revealed that depth of movement is not linearly related to freezing depth or MAAT often used as a proxy for permafrost or freezing conditions, however, colder conditions that enable freezing in general increase depth of movement. Therefore, it is surprising that we found the largest riser height at Turtmann Valley with a MAAT between 0.2 and 3°C. Most other sites are characterized by much colder MAAT, such as Upper Engadin (Matsuoka et al., 2005), the Southern Canadian Rockies (Smith, 1987b), Jotunheimen (Matthews et al., 1998), Tien Shan (Gengnian et al., 1995), Abisko (Ridefelt and Boelhouwers, 2006) or Outpost Mountains (Kinnard and Lewkowicz, 2006), yet all sites except Tien Shan have lobes with lower risers than the Turtmann Valley (Fig. 6c). In addition to freezing temperatures, the efficacy of freezing is controlled by the presence of fine-grained frost susceptible soils. Cohesion at the front is additionally important for riser evolution (Glade et al., 2021), which can result from coarser boulders (Benedict, 1970; Draebing and Eichel, 2017; Harris, 1981) or plant roots (Eichel et al., 2017). Unfortunately, no systematic inventory data is present on these factors, so it remains unsure why the lobes in the Turtmann Valley have such high risers compared to other studies.

Figure 6. Comparison of **a)** lobe width versus riser height, **b)** lobe length versus riser height and **c)** lobe width versus lobe length, with bars indicating the minimum and maximum dimensions measured at a site. Lobe width **d)** and lobe length **e)** versus riser height for turf-banked solifluction lobes in the Turtmann Valley (this study), Outpost Mountain (Hugenholtz and Lewkowicz, 2002) and Upper Engadin (Matsuoka et al., 2005) with the boundaries found by Matsuoka et al., 2005. Upper Engadin data was extracted using WebPlotDigitizer (Rohatgi, 2024). The lobes in the Turtmann Valley clearly differentiate themselves from the lobes in the other studies in terms of length, width, size, L/W ratio and riser height. Yet, in terms of riser height – length and

riser height – width relationship they fall remarkably well within the constraints defined by Matsuoka et al., 2005 (Fig. 6de). Matsuoka et al. (2005) links the boundaries of riser height-width-relationships to horizontal homogeneity of the slope. The minimum boundary ($W = 3H$) indicates that the lobe initiation requires horizontal homogenous slopes supported by data from Outpost Mountain and Engadin and Turtmann Valley (Fig. 6d). Maximum lobe width is controlled by persistence of horizontal homogeneity which is higher at the more gentle slopes at Outpost Mountain (Hugenholtz and Lewkowicz, 2002) in contrast to Alpine sites such as Engadin (Matsuoka et al., 2005) or Turtmann Valley which are characterized by reduced homogeneity due to a large variability of parent slopes and material. For riser height-length-relationships, Matsuoka et al. (2005) explains that the upper boundary ($L = 80H$) is controlled by a combination of debris input into the lobe and climatic conditions, and length stabilizes when sediment availability or climate changes. In this study we use flow accumulation as a proxy for sediment and water input. The high flow accumulations could explain why the lobes in the Turtmann Valley quite closely approach this upper boundary of $80H$, and why the lobes in the Turtmann Valley are generally longer than the ones in different study areas, though we unfortunately have no data on sediment or water influx for the other study areas.

6. Conclusion

Using field, terrain and remote sensing data we investigated dimensions, shape and environmental controls for 40 solifluction lobes in Turtmann Valley. Our analysis shows that:

- i. Largest lobes with highest risers are present in areas of high flow accumulation, likely due to high potential influx of water and sediment.
- ii. Lobe shapes follow a topoclimatic gradient, with wider lobes at higher locations with colder winter temperatures, longer snow duration and low vegetation cover, while elongated, narrower lobes dominated at lower elevations under high, stabilizing vegetation cover, warmer temperatures and less snow cover.

- iii. The lobes we found in Turtmann Valley are longer, more tongue-shaped and thicker than lobes in other Alpine and Arctic mountain ranges due to steeper slopes and possibly increased moisture and sediment availability indicated by high flow accumulation.

Overall, our study suggests that lobe dimensions and shape are controlled strongly by topography and topoclimatic gradients resulting in environmental conditions with steep slopes and increased moisture and sediment availability. Climate change can alter topoclimatic gradients affecting snow cover and duration, moisture availability, ground temperatures and freezing, potentially affecting lobe dimensions like riser height and width.

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